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Classroom Management Skills and Work Performance: Faculty Enhancement Plan

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Abstract

This study determined the classroom management skills and the work performance of the public elementary teachers in the district of Alcantara, Cebu for the school year 2023-2024 as basis for a faculty enhancement plan. This study utilized a descriptive-correlational research design to determine the significant relationship between classroom management skills and the level of work performance of public elementary teachers. There are 98 respondents from the district of Alcantara, Cebu. Under the classroom management skills, teaching skills, Management Skills and interpersonal relations established a significant relationship while discipline and regularity resulted in no significant relationship to the domain Inside the classroom. Organization of the lesson has having significant relationship to discipline regularity and interpersonal relations while it does have a significant relationship to teaching skills and management skills. Strong classroom management skills are vital in creating a positive and conducive learning environment wherein the teachers can increase students' engagement. With this, classroom management skills' impact on work performance goes beyond the teachers' professional reputation. This study recommends the need to foster strong classroom management skills through relevant seminars and workshops, and a program wherein closed monitoring of the application on how to manage a classroom will be supervised.

Keywords: *discipline, main variables, research design, and environment*

Introduction

Good classroom management skills require a fair and reasonable system of classroom rules and procedures that protect and respect students. Teachers are expected to care for the students, their learning, and their personal lives before the students will respect and cooperate with the teachers (Ozgenel & Mert, 2019). Classroom management involves the teacher's actions to create a learning environment that encourages positive and social interaction, active engagement in learning, and self-motivation (Clark et al., 2023; Cabello, 2022). Effective classroom management is a critical element of a highly qualified teacher's repertoire of skills (Mitchell, 2019).

Every district in the Department of Education (DepEd) including the Alcantara District believes that teachers must possess higher classroom management skills for the effective delivery of the teaching-learning process (Özreçberoğlu & Çağanağa, 2018) and this is put into question because acquiring this would take time in rendering higher classroom management skill consistently (Riconalla et al., 2022). An effective classroom manager selects a philosophical model of classroom management and discipline, organizes the physical environment, manages student behavior, creates a respectful, supportive learning environment, manages and facilitates instruction, promotes safety and wellness, and interacts with colleagues, families, and others to achieve classroom management objectives (Burden, 2016).

As revealed, teachers are underprepared for the behaviors that their students may bring to the classroom, resulting in challenges to teaching and learning (Flower et al., 2017). This situation can pose a threat to the work performance of the teachers (Arellano et al., 2024). By definition, work performance indicates how well a teacher is executing the expected related academic activities of the students. Each work performance of the teachers becomes the basic building block of the school performance (Campbell & Wiernik, 2015). The kind of work performance of the teachers determines the quality of graduates (Andriani et al., 2018). These complex job description stifles teachers' work performance and result in several undesirable outcomes (Johari et al., 2018; Dicke et al., 2015).

Classroom management is one of the most cited problems of the basic education teachers (Merc & Subasi, 2015). Studies show that teachers face challenges in dealing with classroom management and workload issues (Lew & Nelson, 2016). Issues such as overcrowded classrooms, classroom discipline, and the organization of classwork often plague teachers in the teaching profession (Macias & Sanchez, 2015). Ihtiyaroglu (2018) examined the connection between the classroom management skills of teachers and their burnout level, work performance, and job satisfaction. Classroom management is likely to represent a very effective resource that should be able to buffer the effects of job demands.

Research Questions

This research determined the classroom management skills and the work performance of the public elementary teachers in the district of Alcantara school year 2023-2024 as a basis for the faculty enhancement plan. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the respondents as to:
 - 1.1. age and gender;
 - 1.2. highest educational attainment;

- 1.3. years in service;
- 1.4. relevant training and seminars attended; and
- 1.5. grade level assignment.
2. What is the level of classroom management skills of the respondents as to:
 - 2.1. inside the classroom;
 - 2.2. organization of the lesson;
 - 2.3. interaction during the lesson;
 - 2.4. teacher-student personal communication; and
 - 2.5. psychological-social classroom environment?
3. What is the level of work performance of the respondents as to:
 - 3.1. teaching skills;
 - 3.2. management skills;
 - 3.3. discipline regularity; and
 - 3.4. interpersonal relations?
4. Is there a significant relationship between:
 - 4.1. profile and level of classroom management skills of the respondents;
 - 4.2. profile and the level of work performance of the respondents and
 - 4.3. classroom management skills level and work performance level of the respondents?
5. Based on the findings, what faculty enhancement plan may be proposed?

Methodology

Research Design

This study utilized a descriptive correlation design. It determined the significant relationship between classroom management skills and the level of work performance of public elementary teachers. The study also tests the correlation of the variables under investigation. In this study, adopted questionnaires on classroom management skills by Diaz et al. (2018) and on work performance by Amin and Atta (2013) will be used.

Respondents

The respondents of the study were public elementary teachers and coordinators in the district of Alcantara during the school year of 2023-2024. There were 25 males and 73 females, a total of 98 respondents that were selected using simple random sampling.

Instrument

The questionnaire has 3 parts. Part I asked the profile of the participants in terms of gender, age, and highest educational attainment years in service and. Part II was an adapted questionnaire on classroom management skills by Diaz et al. (2018) with a Cronbach's alpha of 0.904. This instrument is further divided into five constructs: inside the classroom; organization of the lesson; interaction during the lesson; teacher-student personal communication; and psychological-social classroom environment. There are 60 indicators in total which participants have to answer using a 4-point Likert scale: 4 means usually; 3 means often; 2 means sometimes; and 1 means rarely.

Part III catered to the work performance questionnaire which was also adapted from the study of Amin and Atta (2013) with a reliability coefficient alpha 0.81. It consisted of four constructs: teaching skills; management skills; discipline and regularity; and interpersonal relations. There were a total of 25 indicators which were rated using a 4-point Likert scale: 4 means usually; 3 means often; 2 means sometimes; and 1 means rarely. The instruments were valid and reliable (Cabello & Bonotan, 2021).

Procedure

Preliminary Preparation. The following preliminary preparations were done to make sure that the gathered data were valid: first, the researcher presented the questionnaire to the panel of examiners of the Graduate School of Cebu Technological University – Maolboal Campus for critiquing. Secondly, the researcher prepared a transmittal letter signed by the thesis adviser and Graduate School Dean of CTU Moalboal Campus. Also, the researcher personally submitted the letter to the Schools Division Superintendent of the district of Alcantara for approval to administer the questionnaire to the participants of the study.

Data-Gathering Procedure. The researcher distributed the questionnaires to all participants using simple random sampling. The administration of the questionnaires was done last July 2023. The researcher presented the approved letter and made a dialogue with the school heads regarding the study. The researchers set a date, as agreed by the school heads, to retrieve the questionnaires. Finally, the data was collected, tabulated, analyzed, and statistically interpreted.

Data Analysis

The following statistical treatments were used in this study. Frequency and Simple Percentage. This was used to present the profile of

the participants. Weighted Mean. This was used to analyze the classroom management skills and work performance of the participants. Weighted Mean and Standard Deviation. These were used to identify the level of the respondents' classroom management skills and work performance. Pearson *r*. This was used to establish the significant relationships among the demographic profile, classroom management skills, and work performance. Test of Independence. This was used to test the relationship of the variables of the study.

Results and Discussion

The tables and discussion below are anchored on how the statement of the problem is being answered in this study.

Respondents' Demographic Profile

Table 1. Age

Age	Frequency	Percentage
40 and above	29	30%
35 - 39 years old	13	13%
30 - 34 years old	22	22%
25 - 29 years old	28	29%
24 – and below	6	6%
Total	98	100%

The table shows the age of the respondents. It can be seen that two brackets are of almost the same percentage, the 40 and above with 29 counts (30%) and the 25-29 years old with counts (29%) brackets dominate the age brackets of the respondents. The lowest count goes to the newly hired teachers aging from 24 and below with 6 counts (6%). This means that the data is well distributed. The age of the respondents is a crucial factor when classroom management and work performance are the constructs of a research study (Lazarides et al., 2020).

Classroom management is the way how a teacher can bring the classroom into a conducive one maintaining a positive atmosphere wherein the disruptive behavior of the students will be avoided (Nisar et al., 2019). Having a good command of classroom management established a good impact on work performance. Age is a factor in handling the classroom and achieving job satisfaction at work (Moltudal et al., 2019). Most of the teachers in the research environment are already aging in their familiarity and exposure to classroom scenarios is unquestionable and undeniably vast.

Table 2. Gender

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Male	25	25%
Female	73	75%
Total	98	100%

The table presents the gender of the respondents. It can be seen that the majority of the respondents are female with 73 counts (75%) while male teachers composed 25% of the total sample size. This data implies that in this teaching profession, women are more inclined to it. This is also in connection with how the teaching profession is viewed in society wherein most female students established their early preference in the field of teaching (Adedigba & Sulaiman, 2020).

Gender is one of the most essential elements of classroom management and work performance (Valente et al., 2020). This can be traced back to how the female teachers comfortably bring the classroom into a home-like atmosphere where students can feel at ease and will have fun while they are learning (Kowalski & Froiland, 2020). Gender is an indicator of how well the teachers can manage the class in terms of making decisions and improving the process of delivering quality instruction.

Table 3. Highest Educational Attainment

Highest Educational Attainment	Frequency	Percentage
With 18 units in Masters	53	54%
With Comprehensive Academic Requirements in Masters	27	28%
Master's Degree Holder	17	17%
With at least 24 units in Doctoral	1	1%
With Comprehensive Academic Requirements in Doctoral	0	0%
Doctoral Degree Holder	0	0%
Total	98	100%

Table presents the respondents' highest educational attainment. It can be gleaned that the majority of the respondents are already on the verge of pursuing their advanced education wherein 53 teachers (54%) acquired at least 18 units of masteral units. In the data above, none was able to proceed with the comprehensive academic requirements of a doctoral degree, one respondent (1%) acquired at least 24 units in doctoral. This means that the respondents of this study are working towards their professional advancement (Santos & Miguel, 2019).

Attaining degree advancement in the educational field is not just for practical purposes but also for classroom improvement (Smith &

Gillespie, 2023). The target of advanced education is not to be promoted personally but to allow all learners to be promoted to the next level of learning experiences (Evans et al., 2020). The need to be exposed to the different classroom management prerogatives is significant to carry out the vision and mission of the department and the main intent to provide quality learning experiences (Popova et al., 2022). Having to continue advanced education means that a professional is always welcoming updates on how to bring the teaching-learning process into the limelight.

Table 4. *Years in Service*

<i>Years in Service</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Below 5 years	40	41%
6-10 years	25	26%
11-15 years	11	11%
16-20 years	11	11%
21-25 years	10	10%
26-30 years	1	1%
31 years and above	0	0%
Total	98	100%

The table presents the respondents' years in service of teaching. It can be gleaned that most of the teachers have below 5 years of experience with 40 counts (41%). The lowest frequency in the bracket of the years in experience is 26 – 30 years with 1 count while no one serves the institution for more than 31 years. This data gives the impression the respondents of this research are new to the teaching profession. The age of the respondents does not necessarily mean that they are aging, they also have a long time staying in the department because some teachers rendered different jobs before settling in the government (Owens et al., 2020).

The respondents' years in service are essential in managing a classroom, wherein the variety of teaching experiences is a reference to the true meaning of learning opportunities (Poulou et al., 2019). The need to acquire experience in classroom situations, especially in classroom management skills and reaching job satisfaction, is a requisite to be sharp and effective in teaching (Podolsky et al., 2019). Having several years of experience does not undermine those teachers who are newly hired, as they possess skills and abilities to answer the needs of society.

Table 5. *Relevant Training and Seminars Attended*

<i>Relevant Training and Seminars Attended</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Local	37	38%
National	59	60%
International	2	2%
Total	98	100%

The table presents the relevant training and seminars attended. It can be gleaned that most of the respondents attended the national training and seminar with 59 counts (60%). While the lowest count goes to those who attended the international training and seminar with 2 counts (2%). This data implies that the respondents usually attend local and national training and seminars while less in the international arena for some practical reasons and the availability of resources (Garcia & Weiss, 2019).

Having an attendance in the international training and seminar that would last for 3 to 5 days with personal expenses in food, transportation and accommodation can be very draining (Cirocki & Farrell, 2019). It is discouraging to see how much expenditure is extended while getting limited benefits. Although, in the international training and seminar, different cultures and diverse audiences with essential learning experiences can be achieved, however, because of the technological influences, these experiences can be learned (Padillo et al., 2021). Classroom management from different parts of the globe can be watched through digital tools.

Table 6. *Respondents' Grade Level Assignment*

<i>Grade Level Assignment</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Kindergarten	6	6%
Grade 1	14	14%
Grade 2	13	13%
Grade 3	16	17%
Grade 4	22	23%
Grade 5	12	12%
Grade 6	15	15%
Total	98	100%

The table presents the respondents' grade level of assignment. It can be seen that most of the teachers are coming from the grade 4 level with 22 counts (23%). The lowest count is in the kindergarten level with 6 counts (6%). The data suggests that since most of the respondents are coming from the grade 4 level, it is a good ground to look for the perspective of the lens of knowing how teachers manage the classroom management and work performance in the middle of the grade level (Wang et al., 2020). The data also implies that there are a limited number of kindergarten teachers because usually in a school, the least number of teachers is in the kindergarten.

In connecting the respondents' grade level assignment to the teacher's classroom management and work performance, each grade level experiences different experiences because the kinds of learners differ (Bottiani et al., 2019). Teachers will have varying ways and classroom management skills in handling the teaching-learning process. Achieving an increase in work performance can be manifested when everyone shares different best practices in classroom management in the different grade-level assignments.

Classroom Management Skills

The teachers' classroom management skills are vital in sustaining the delivery of quality education. It is important to look into these skills and how it contribute to the work performance of the learners. When the teachers' work performance is on the pedestal, the academic performance of the learners will also improve.

Table 7. *Inside the Classroom*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>
I involve students in establishing rules and procedures.	3.73	0.44
I share with students the reasons behind the disciplinary approach(es) I use.	3.52	0.60
I provide positive reinforcement to students for appropriate behavior (e.g. special helper, extra computer time, tangible rewards)	3.62	0.60
I make students aware of consequences for misbehavior (e.g. loss of break time, extra classroom time)	3.58	0.66
I use class time to reflect on appropriate behavior with students as a group.	3.52	0.89
I redirect inappropriate behavior on the spot, using loud voice.	2.81	1.03
I ignore misbehavior that is non-disruptive to class.	2.79	1.08
I use short verbal cues to stop misbehavior (e.g. say student's name aloud, use "shh" sound).	3.14	0.80
I use nonverbal signals to stop misbehavior (e.g. make eye contact, approach and touch disruptive students).	3.42	0.75
I use self-assessment forms for students to evaluate their own behavior (e.g. checklists).	3.22	0.79
I inform parents about classroom expectations.	3.36	0.58
I send for parents to report inappropriate behavior.	3.22	0.88
I send for parents to report good behavior.	3.34	0.77
I collaborate with parents on a homeschool behavior plan.	3.27	0.74
I teach parents activities to do with students at home to reinforce good behavior at school.	3.13	0.78
I inform parents about the policies regarding the use of mobile phones at school.	3.49	0.72
I inform parents about social networks and their correct use (e.g. "Facebook", "Twitter", "Instagram").	3.32	0.82
I send home Teacher-to-Parent Communication letters or newsletters regarding positive and negative aspects of their children's behavior.	3.08	0.89
I send students home for aggressive or disruptive behavior.	2.70	1.15
I send students to the principal's office for misbehavior	2.73	1.13
AWM	3.25	0.81

The table presents the classroom management skills specifically the domain under Inside the classroom. It can be gleaned that the statement, "I involve students in establishing rules and procedures." garnered a mean score of 3.73 with a standard deviation of 0.44. While the statement, "I send students home for aggressive or disruptive behavior." gained the lowest mean score of 2.70 with a standard deviation of 1.15. The data above implies that in handling classroom management skills specifically inside the classroom, it is important to involve the learners in the process of making and establishing the rules and regulations. In this way, they will feel that they are valued because they are heard and they are part of the process (Franklin & Harrington, 2019).

The need to have great participation among the learners underscores the fact that the initial point of engagement is to set the mood of the classroom by establishing the rules and regulations (McGarr, 2021; Baisac et al., 2022). When learners are part of the process, they will feel the great leap of accountability (Gomez et al., 2024). It is hard to disobey a law, rule, or policy that one creates (Simonsen et al., 2020). The data also suggests that when students are aggressive or have disruptive behavior, they should not be sent home. Instead, their concerns and the root of their disruptive behavior should be deliberated and provided appropriate measures so that they will not feel ignored.

The table 8 presents the respondents' classroom management skills in the organization of the lesson. It can be gleaned that the statement, "I take into account students' previous knowledge to plan the activities based on their level." garnered the highest mean of 3.58 with a standard deviation of 0.57. The lowest mean of 3.24 with a standard deviation of 0.77 goes to the statement, "I use different types of seating arrangements depending on the type of activity students are assigned to do." This means that in organizing the lesson as part of the classroom management skills, it is important to verify and check the schema or the background knowledge of the learners. The teacher must know what topic that should be reiterated because it was part of the missed topic in the previous level. Teachers should also provide a seating arrangement that is anchored or appropriate to the design of the learning tasks (Nagro et al., 2019).

Organizing the lesson is vital in sustaining a well-managed classroom. This is when the teachers make sure that the intended learning outcome is constructively aligned to the academic tasks and how it will be assessed (Prilop et al., 2021; Gabriel et al., 2022). It is important to conduct a formative assessment wherein the knowledge of the learners will be assessed. The teacher can facilitate an appropriate method to address the learning needs of the learners. When this is achieved, the lessons will be delivered in a systematic and organized manner (Setyaningsih & Suchyadi, 2021). Along with the process of making appropriate methods, the physical

environment of the classroom should be conducive in such a way that the seating arrangement is properly designed for a certain purpose.

Table 8. *Organization of the Lesson*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>
I take into account different learning styles when preparing the lesson.	3.52	0.60
I take into account students' previous knowledge to plan the activities based on their level.	3.58	0.57
I establish routines for group work when needed.	3.49	0.61
I start the lesson by giving students an opportunity to set their own learning goals.	3.44	0.64
I make sure that the learning goals are clearly stated for students to understand them (e.g. displaying them on the board, saying them out loud).	3.52	0.66
I organize the activities into logical stages to fulfill the objectives of the lesson.	3.39	0.70
I use different types of seating arrangements depending on the type of activity students are assigned to do.	3.24	0.77
I prepare students for transitions and interactions (e.g. bathroom rules, moving from one classroom to another) using predictable routines.	3.27	0.73
I create extra activities for students to work when they have completed their main task.	3.56	0.61
I assign advanced students as assistants to help weaker learners in the completion of their tasks.	3.45	0.66
AWM	3.45	0.66

The table 9 shows the respondents' classroom management skills in providing an interactive way of delivering classroom instruction. The results revealed that learners learned and classroom management is upheld when simple language is being used. This manifested in the statement that garnered the highest mean of 3.73 with a standard deviation of 0.47 which stated that "I keep English simple and clear (e.g. trying to pronounce every word well, using appropriate pacing according to students' English level)". The statement, "I finish the class with a reflection activity about the lesson (e.g. written reflection, oral reflection, report on what was learned)." marked the lowest mean of 3.20 with a standard deviation of 0.81. This implies that when there is clarity in the discussion, learners will be engaged wherein their focus will be sustained (Wut & Xu, 2021).

Table 9. *Interaction During the Lesson*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>
I start the lesson in an unusual manner to catch students' attention (e.g. telling an amusing story or personal anecdote; starting in a very quiet or low voice).	3.37	0.75
I model the task to demonstrate what students are expected to do (e.g. role playing the task with a student, assigning a student to demonstrate the task).	3.34	0.64
I use concept check questions to make sure instructions are understood (e.g. "what do you have to do first?", "do you have to work in pairs or in groups?").	3.41	0.67
I use body language to make instructions understandable.	3.23	0.67
I keep English simple and clear (e.g. trying to pronounce every word well, using appropriate pacing according to students' English level).	3.73	0.47
I monitor students' work spending equal amount of time in all quadrants of the classroom.	3.55	0.58
I respond to students' answers using verbal praising (e.g. "Brilliant!", "Great!", "Nice job!").	3.56	0.54
I respond to students' incorrect answers validating students' participation (e.g. "that's partly correct", "good effort").	3.47	0.56
I give students instructions on how to report their completed work.	3.57	0.56
I finish the class with a reflection activity about the lesson (e.g. written reflection, oral reflection, report on what was learnt).	3.20	0.81
AWM	3.44	0.63

In the process of delivering classroom instruction, the best way to convey the message is through the utilization of simple English as the medium of discussion. Good classroom management can be observed when learners interact with one another and consistently work to achieve the desired intended learning outcome (Hew et al., 2020). This can be materialized when teachers are communicating in the best way possible. It is also important to have reflection after the classroom discussion wherein the learners can assess what specific objectives are attained (Kohnke & Moorhouse, 2022; Catulpos et al., 2024). Reflection can be done in a self-assessment procedure so that a learner can see what went through and what went well in the classroom interaction (Taneo et al., 2023).

The table 10 presents the respondents' classroom management skills in teacher-student personal communication. It can be gleaned that the highest mean of 3.68 with a standard deviation of 0.53 goes to the statement, "I use eye contact to make students feel I care about what they say and do.". The statement, "I attempt to be "Me" rather than "the Teacher" to make students feel I am approachable." garnered the lowest mean of 3.30 with a standard deviation of 0.78. This means that in the teacher-student communication, it is crucial to establish a good eye contact. In this way, learners can feel that there is a close connection between their understanding and the lessons presented by the teacher (Scherzinger & Wettstein, 2019).

Classroom management skills specifically in the teacher-student personal communication, the need to be sincere in delivering the lesson should be felt by the learners so that they can reciprocate (Elhay & Hershkovitz, 2019; Bohol et al., 2024). Having good eye-to-eye contact with the learners is tantamount to maintaining their focus. When teachers are looking at the learners' eyes, learners are motivated to be still and maximize their attention span (Obispo et al., 2021). In this way, the teacher is teaching not because of the

lessons to be delivered but the inclusion of feelings such that teachers can feel the learners' needs.

Table 10. *Teacher-Student Personal Communication*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>
I attempt to be "Me" rather than "the Teacher" to make students feel I am approachable.	3.30	0.78
I learn students' names to recognize them as individuals.	3.63	0.53
I interact with students as individuals.	3.67	0.55
I use eye contact to make students feel I care about what they say and do.	3.68	0.53
I learn about the different types of students' personal and social needs (e.g. using 'getting to know each other activities', questionnaires).	3.45	0.61
I incorporate students' personal interests into teaching.	3.57	0.54
I encourage creativity and self-expression in students.	3.59	0.55
I talk with students' previous teachers to gather information about students.	3.49	0.66
I praise individual accomplishments and important events in students' lives.	3.65	0.58
I talk with a student after an emotional outburst to demonstrate I am personally interested in him/her.	3.33	0.61
AWM	3.54	0.59

The table 11 shows the respondents' classroom management skills in establishing a psychological and social classroom environment. Among the indicators, the statement, "I promote positive social values (e.g. helping, sharing, being patient)." garnered the highest mean of 3.74 with a standard deviation of 0.46. The statement, "I begin the lesson with activities to reinforce a sense of collaboration among students." gained the lowest mean of 3.51 with a standard deviation of 0.60. This means that in making the classroom environment psychologically sound, teachers should not miss promoting positive social values in which the learners can appreciate what positive things they have done (Dornyei & Muir, 2019).

Table 11. *Psychological and Social Classroom Environment*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>
I begin the lesson with activities to reinforce a sense of collaboration among students.	3.51	0.60
I encourage students to be respectful one another.	3.66	0.57
I promote positive social values (e.g. helping, sharing, being patient).	3.74	0.46
I encourage students to reach an agreement through conversations to resolve any issue.	3.59	0.53
I teach students to work together cooperatively toward academic goals.	3.62	0.58
I use problem solving scenarios with students to develop their problem-solving skills.	3.58	0.59
I promote students' responsibility in my classroom practice.	3.63	0.54
I promote respect for cultural diversity in the classroom.	3.55	0.61
I help students to become aware of their own thinking.	3.64	0.52
I help students to develop their ability to make decisions by themselves.	3.62	0.51
AWM	3.61	0.55

Sustaining a positive environment is not easy. Learners normally would explore and during their exploration, the classroom will not be as tidy as what teachers want (Bedir, 2023). It is in the teacher's command how to make the classroom conducive not just to learning but also to acquiring social values (Brackett et al., 2019). Providing reinforcement activities are encouraged to see how learners are communicating, collaborating, and helping one another to achieve the desired output.

Respondents' Work Performance

The respondents' work performance is composed of the respondents' teaching skills, management skills, discipline and regularity, and interpersonal relations. These indicators are essential in evaluating the effectiveness of the teacher's classroom management strategies and techniques.

Table 12. *Teaching Skills*

<i>Statements</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>
I use different methods of teaching.	3.61	0.55
Most of students of my class get good marks.	3.34	0.62
I teach every student according to his abilities.	3.49	0.58
I come well prepared for teaching in class.	3.55	0.56
I can also teach difficult lessons easily.	3.24	0.64
If any student asks question, I try to satisfy him at every level.	3.57	0.59
I make no injustice in marking the papers.	3.24	0.80
AWM	3.42	0.62

The table presents the respondents' work performance in teaching skills. It can be gleaned that in the data, the statement, "I use different methods of teaching." garnered the highest mean of 3.61 with a standard deviation of 0.55. The statements, "I make no injustice in marking the papers." and "I can also teach difficult lessons easily." Gained the lowest mean of 3.24 with a standard deviation of 0.64 and 0.80 respectively. This implies that in teaching, it is important to use multiple methods because this will address the diversity of learners and their needs (Murkatik et al., 2020).

Teaching skills can be honed through different learning experiences inside the classroom (Baluyos et al., 2019; Papay et al., 2020). Teaching easy subjects and difficult ones are just the same. Teachers should teach these lessons with proper preparation and due diligence (Li & Wang, 2021). Teachers should not make mistakes in marking papers and make sure to teach difficult subject in an easy manner that learners can learn (Kartini et al., 2020; Hoque et al., 2020). Teaching difficult subjects can become an easy task when this is coupled with different teaching methodologies.

Table 13. *Management Skills*

<i>Statements</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>
Apart from teaching I fulfill other responsibilities very nicely.	3.56	0.56
I don't let co-curricular activities to affect my class teaching.	3.22	0.86
I don't let my domestic affairs to interfere in my duty.	3.45	0.73
If someone changes my responsibilities, then I adjust myself.	3.44	0.67
I am good in dealing failures and setbacks and always choose to protect the welfare in class teaching.	3.35	0.72
I help my teachers develop their full potentials.	3.48	0.61
I try my best to improve the level of my performance.	3.68	0.49
AWM	3.45	0.66

The table presents the respondents' work performance in managing a classroom. It can be gleaned that the statement, "I try my best to improve the level of my performance." garnered the highest mean 3.68 with a standard deviation of 0.49. The statement, "I don't let co-curricular activities affect my class teaching." gained the lowest mean of 3.22 with a standard deviation of 0.86. This data implies that in honing the teachers' management skills, one must give the best. Giving one's best is not the same as giving it with perfection. Best is a construct-relative defined as the extent of how genuinely someone can perform to the utmost level of exhausting all possible resources (Hartinah et al., 2020).

Managing the classroom is one of the domains of work performance in teaching because it captures the essence of the main responsibility of being a teacher – to manage the classroom (Khan & Abdullah, 2019). Being a manager inside the classroom, academic and co-curricular activities are monitored and regulated however, it should not compromise the intended learning outcome which teachers should prioritize (Ozgenel & Mert, 2019). Teachers as managers should know how to manage not just the lessons to be delivered but also the time element budgeted for every learning competency.

Table 14. *Discipline and Regularity*

<i>Statements</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>
I come to school regularly.	3.78	0.44
When present at school I attain my class on time.	3.67	0.53
I don't do irrelevant activity in my period.	3.50	0.60
I fulfill my assigned activities on time.	3.61	0.53
I complete my syllabus on time.	3.54	0.56
I maintain discipline in my class.	3.57	0.57
I monitor the class fairly and productively.	3.65	0.52
AWM	3.62	0.54

The table shows the respondents' work performance in discipline and regularity. It can be gleaned that the statement, "I come to school regularly." marked the highest mean of 3.78 with a standard deviation of 0.44. The statement, "I don't do irrelevant activity in my period." garnered the lowest mean of 3.50 with a standard deviation of 0.60. This means that when teachers are imposing the approved and agreed rules and regulations inside the classroom such as coming to school early, it should be followed and teachers should be role models (Mahmood et al., 2021).

Discipline and regularity are important in sustaining good classroom management which can impact the work performance of the learners (Sittar, 2020). Discipline should be seen by the learners for the learners to follow. When teachers come to school late, it is very hard for these teachers to uphold discipline in time management (Bahadar et al., 2023). Learners will always have that impression to walk the talk. A teacher is a role model. Learners are looking up to how teachers exemplify the right attitude and behavior especially the proper way of upholding discipline and regularity (Mahmood et al., 2021).

Table 15. *Interpersonal Relations*

<i>Statements</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>
Apart from teaching I try to solve any problem of the student.	3.56	0.56
I enjoy good relations with my colleagues.	3.69	0.56
I co-operate with my colleagues in any work.	3.61	0.51
I consult my colleagues in solving of my class problems.	3.51	0.68
I motivate my students to take part in co-curricular activities.	3.55	0.52
For the betterment of my students, I contact their parents.	3.54	0.56
I help the head in solving the problems of the school.	3.23	0.87
AWM	3.53	0.61

The table shows the respondents' work performance in interpersonal relations. It can be seen in the indicators that the statement, "I enjoy good relations with my colleagues." gained the highest mean of 3.69 with a standard deviation of 0.56. The statement, "I help the head in solving the problems of the school." garnered the lowest mean of 3.23 with a standard deviation of 0.87. This means that in the working environment, establishing a camaraderie spirit among colleagues is vital to staying in the workplace (Xie & Derakhshan, 2021). It is also important to contribute something to the success of the organizational goals and objectives.

Interpersonal relations can be a source of workplace support wherein co-workers or co-teachers are helping one another (Kara, 2020). Having a good sense of relations among others can motivate more in improving work ethics. Helping the head of the organization or in a school can be both advantageous and disadvantageous. This can be misinterpreted by some of the teachers (Greenier et al., 2021). The best way possible to enrich interpersonal relations is to be neutral and to always establish good relations with others. In this way, conflict will be avoided.

Significant Relationship

The significant relationship between and among the variables is essential in making a faculty enhancement plan. This is to determine what factors affect the implementation of classroom management strategies and techniques. In this study, the significant relationship among the respondents' demographic profiles such as age, gender, highest educational attainment, years of experience, relevant training and seminars, and the teachers' grade level assignment to the classroom management such as inside the classroom, organization of the lesson, interaction during the lesson, student-teacher personal communication, and the psychological and social classroom environment are being identified.

Table 16. *Significant Relationship between the Respondents' Demographic Profile and Level of Classroom Management Skills*

		R-value	p-value	Interpretation	Decision
Age		0.60	0.56	Not Significant	Failed to Reject the Null Hypothesis
Gender		0.79	0.03	Significant	Reject the Null Hypothesis
Highest Educational Attainment	Inside the	0.17	0.01	Significant	Reject the Null Hypothesis
Years of Experience	Classroom	0.67	0.06	Not Significant	Failed to Reject the Null Hypothesis
Relevant Seminars and Training		0.58	0.05	Significant	Reject the Null Hypothesis
Grade Level Assignment		0.26	0.01	Significant	Reject the Null Hypothesis

The table presents the significant relationship between the demographic profile and the classroom management skills inside the classroom domain. It can be gleaned that gender (0.03), highest educational attainment (0.01), relevant training and seminars (0.05), and grade level assignment (0.01) established a significant relationship whereas age and years of experience established a not significant result. This means that managing inside the classroom can be influenced by several indicators in the demographic profile. The advanced education attained by the teachers and the relevant training and seminars are tantamount to how a teacher manages inside the classroom (Gaias et al., 2019).

Inside the classroom, there are several factors to consider especially when establishing good classroom management (Clark et al., 2023). Teachers should be cognizant of the need to conduct classes with a wide array of understanding in the teaching profession which can be acquired when one is pursuing advanced education (Debbag & Fidan, 2020). Although years of teaching establish a not significant effect, it is still important to consider the need to learn from the experiences and exposures inside the classroom for many years (Gilmour et al., 2022). This can make the teacher ready to handle a class upholding quality education.

Table 17. *Significant Relationship between the Respondents' Demographic Profile and Organization of the Lesson*

		R-value	p-value	Interpretation	Decision
Age		0.71	0.03	Significant	Reject the Null Hypothesis
Gender		0.08	0.41	Not Significant	Failed to Reject the Null Hypothesis
Highest Educational Attainment	Organization	0.64	0.05	Significant	Reject the Null Hypothesis
Years of Experience	of the Lesson	0.21	0.04	Significant	Reject the Null Hypothesis
Relevant Seminars and Training		0.06	0.05	Significant	Reject the Null Hypothesis
Grade Level Assignment		0.85	0.40	Not Significant	Failed to Reject the Null Hypothesis

The table shows the significant relationship between the respondents' demographic profile and the organization of the lesson. The results revealed that age (0.03), highest educational attainment (0.05), years of experience (0.04), and relevant training and seminars (0.05) attended established a significant relationship to the organization of the lesson as one of the classroom management skills. Gender and grade level assignment established no significant effect on how a teacher organizes the class. This means that when the teacher is already aging, the way how the lessons are delivered would be different from those who are still young. Experience is the best but the young ones can learn from the experiences of the veteran teachers (Hepburn et al., 2021).

Classroom management skills necessitate several factors to take into account. Organizing the lesson to be shared inside the classroom must be presented well so that quality education is sustained (Nisar et al., 2019). Acquiring relevant training and seminars in classroom management can help teachers forward a very organized lesson presentation (Simonsen et al., 2020). The years of experience are an

added advantage because of the exposure to how to deal with classroom distractions and other negative classroom constraints (Mitchell, 2019). Having post-graduate units such as master's and doctoral can help teachers how to understand learners' behavior.

Table 18. *Significant Relationship between the Respondents' Demographic Profile and Interaction During the Lesson*

		<i>R-value</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>	<i>Decision</i>
Age		0.18	0.07	Not Significant	Failed to Reject the Null Hypothesis
Gender		0.07	0.04	Significant	Reject the Null Hypothesis
Highest Educational Attainment	Interaction During the Lesson	0.06	0.05	Significant	Reject the Null Hypothesis
Years of Experience		0.10	0.31	Not Significant	Failed to Reject the Null Hypothesis
Relevant Seminars and Training		0.06	0.05	Significant	Reject the Null Hypothesis
Grade Level Assignment		0.09	0.00	Significant	Reject the Null Hypothesis

The table shows the significant relationship between the respondents' demographic profile and their classroom management skills in establishing an interaction during the lesson. It can be gleaned that gender (0.04), highest educational attainment (0.05), relevant training and seminars (0.05), and grade level assignment (0.00) established a significant relationship while age and years of experience revealed no significant relationship to the interaction during the lesson as classroom management skill. This means that in establishing the interaction of the lesson in the classroom factors under demographic profile are to be taken into account so that quality education will be sustained in the educative process (Yoon & Kim, 2022).

Interaction inside the classroom is very important in the learners' academic journey. It is where the learners are given the chance to share their ideas and learn from each other (Wolff et al., 2021). Gender plays an important role in connecting with the learners. The compassion extended to the learners will matter if it is a female or a male teacher. Advanced education and attending training and seminars create different opportunities to make the discussion inside the classroom substantive (Jerome et al., 2020). The grade level assignment impacts how teachers are handling the classroom since the kind of approach and methods to be used would matter to the learners in a particular grade level.

Table 19. *Significant Relationship between the Respondents' Demographic Profile and Teacher-Student Personal Communication*

		<i>R-value</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>	<i>Decision</i>
Age		0.27	0.00	Not Significant	Failed to Reject the Null Hypothesis
Gender	Teacher- Student Personal Communication	0.09	0.01	Not Significant	Failed to Reject the Null Hypothesis
Highest Educational Attainment		0.57	0.05	Significant	Reject the Null Hypothesis
Years of Experience		0.14	0.15	Not Significant	Failed to Reject the Null Hypothesis
Relevant Seminars and Training		0.07	0.04	Significant	Reject the Null Hypothesis
Grade Level Assignment		0.10	0.30	Not Significant	Failed to Reject the Null Hypothesis

The table presents the significant relationship between the respondents' demographic profile and the teacher-student personal communication. It can be seen that the results revealed a significant relationship between age (0.00), gender (0.01), highest educational attainment (0.05), and the relevant training and seminars (0.04) to the teacher-student personal communication. While years of teaching experience and grade-level assignments resulted in no significant relationship to the teacher-student personal communication. This means that the teachers' educational attainment and relevant training and seminars can help in building trust and a supportive learning environment (Cho et al., 2020).

Teacher-student personal communication provides a sense of connection inside the classroom wherein students are motivated to interact with one another (Demir & Sad, 2021). When teachers establish personal communication, they can provide guidance and address learning needs and gaps wherein a positive learning environment can be sustained (Chuang et al., 2020). Consistent interpersonal relationships can pave the way to effective teaching and a more enriching educational experience (Stevenson et al., 2020). This can also have a domino effect on teachers' work performance.

Table 20. *Significant Relationship between the Respondents' Demographic Profile and Psychological and Social Classroom Environment*

		<i>R-value</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>	<i>Decision</i>
Age		0.15	0.14	Not Significant	Failed to Reject the Null Hypothesis
Gender	Psychological and Social Classroom Environment	0.55	0.06	Not Significant	Failed to Reject the Null Hypothesis
Highest Educational Attainment		0.79	0.02	Significant	Reject the Null Hypothesis
Years of Experience		0.06	0.05	Significant	Reject the Null Hypothesis
Relevant Seminars and Training		0.54	0.61	Not Significant	Failed to Reject the Null Hypothesis
Grade Level Assignment		0.72	0.03	Significant	Reject the Null Hypothesis

The table presents the significant relationship between the respondents' demographic profile and classroom management skills in establishing a psychological and social classroom environment. It can be gleaned that the highest educational attainment (0.02), years of teaching experience (0.05), and grade level assignment (0.03) established a significant relationship to the psychological and social

classroom environment while age, gender, and relevant training and seminars do not establish a significant relationship (Bakola et al., 2019).

Having a positive psychological and social environment captures a classroom where learners are valued and when trust and support prevail (Dornyei & Muir, 2019; Valente et al., 2019). Open communication should be observed so that there will be active listening and empathy for one another (Kim et al., 2019). It is through utilizing multiple methods and strategies that teachers can enrich social connections while appreciating diversity and individual differences (Alexopoulou et al., 2019). When teachers promote social connections, learners can feel safe and ready to be engaged in classroom discussions. This can improve classroom management skills.

Table 21. Significant Relationship between the Respondents' Demographic Profile and Teaching Skills

		<i>R-value</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>	<i>Decision</i>
Age		0.43	0.08	Not Significant	Failed to Reject the Null Hypothesis
Gender		0.36	0.09	Not Significant	Failed to Reject the Null Hypothesis
Highest Educational Attainment	Teaching Skills	0.75	0.03	Significant	Reject the Null Hypothesis
Years of Experience		0.87	0.01	Significant	Reject the Null Hypothesis
Relevant Seminars and Training		0.33	0.09	Not Significant	Failed to Reject the Null Hypothesis
Grade Level Assignment		0.42	0.08	Not Significant	Failed to Reject the Null Hypothesis

The table shows the significant relationship between the respondents' demographic profile and the teacher's work performance, specifically in their teaching skills. It can be gleaned that the teachers' highest educational attainment (0.03) and years of teaching experience (0.01) established a significant relationship to their teaching skills. Age, gender, relevant training and seminars, and the grade level assignment do not have a significant relationship to the teaching skills of the teachers. This means that when teachers acquire advanced education and spend many years in the service, their teaching skills may bring nuanced methods and strategies to make the classroom conducive to learning (Kirkpatrick et al., 2019).

The teaching skills of the teachers can be influenced by their highest educational attainment and years of teaching experience which they learned from the advanced education that they pursued and the lecture from the relevant training and seminars attended (Byrd & Alexander, 2020). Having this notion, teachers can target specific learning competencies that should be focused on. Teaching skills are the ability of a teacher to facilitate a learning environment through lesson planning, classroom management and routines, addressing diverse learning needs, and effective communication in delivering quality education (Gultom et al., 2020). Understanding the different factors affecting teaching skills can exemplify what teaching skills as part of the teachers' work performance is all about.

Table 22. Significant Relationship between the Respondents' Demographic Profile and Management Skills

		<i>R-value</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>	<i>Decision</i>
Age		0.22	0.03	Significant	Reject the Null Hypothesis
Gender		0.57	0.05	Significant	Reject the Null Hypothesis
Highest Educational Attainment	Management Skills	0.10	0.03	Significant	Reject the Null Hypothesis
Years of Experience		0.26	0.11	Not Significant	Failed to Reject the Null Hypothesis
Relevant Seminars and Training		0.86	0.02	Significant	Reject the Null Hypothesis
Grade Level Assignment		0.07	0.42	Not Significant	Failed to Reject the Null Hypothesis

Table reveals the significant relationship of the respondents' demographic profile to teachers' management skills. It can be gleaned that age (0.03), gender (0.05), highest educational attainment (0.03), and relevant training and seminars (0.02) established a significant relationship to teachers' management skills while the years of teaching experience and the grade level assignment established a no significant relationship. This means that management skills can be influenced by the teachers' age, gender, the acquired educational attainment and the relevant training and seminars attended (Tang, 2020).

Having management skills in the field of teaching can greatly affect the classroom atmosphere, especially in establishing a positive and conducive learning environment (Sanjar & Doston, 2022). Acquiring a good command of management skills promotes a well-organized classroom, effective teaching, and the ability to provide clear expectations inside the classroom (Kniaz & Chukhno, 2021). With these, teachers can address behavioral issues and challenges in the teaching-learning process (Herman, 2020). The ability to manage and maximize the different resources and the utilization of multiple methods in addressing the diverse needs of the learners are key components of an effective teacher using management skills.

Table 23. Significant Relationship between the Respondents' Demographic Profile and Discipline and Regularity

		<i>R-value</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>	<i>Decision</i>
Age		0.81	0.02	Significant	Reject the Null Hypothesis
Gender		0.38	0.08	Not Significant	Failed to Reject the Null Hypothesis
Highest Educational Attainment	Discipline and Regularity	0.69	0.04	Significant	Reject the Null Hypothesis
Years of Experience		0.11	0.27	Not Significant	Failed to Reject the Null Hypothesis
Relevant Seminars and Training		0.56	0.05	Significant	Reject the Null Hypothesis
Grade Level Assignment		0.16	0.10	Not Significant	Failed to Reject the Null Hypothesis

The table shows the significant relationship between the respondents' demographic profile and the work performance of teachers toward discipline and regularity inside the classroom. It can be gleaned that the age (0.02), the highest educational attainment (0.04), and the relevant training and seminars attended (0.05) established a significant relationship to discipline and regularity. Gender, years of teaching experience, and grade level assignment established no significant relationship to discipline and regularity. This means that in terms of establishing discipline, the age of the teacher will matter as the old ones followed the traditional way and the young ones introduced the way how to understand the attitude of the new generation (Azainil et al., 2021).

Discipline and regularity are two important elements in carrying out the intended learning outcome in a class discussion (Xudayberdieva & Shodmonov, 2020). Discipline sets the order so that when the teaching-learning process is facilitated, limited time is given to reprimand which increases classroom productivity (Zikanga et al., 2021). Since discipline refers to the student's adherence to the rules and regulations inside the classroom, regularity is more concerned with the consistency of adhering to the agreed rules so that disruptive behavior will be avoided. Maintaining a well-disciplined classroom fosters sound communication where teachers can facilitate learning well.

Table 24. Significant Relationship between the Respondents' Demographic Profile and Interpersonal Relations

		R-value	p-value	Interpretation	Decision
Age		0.16	0.10	Not Significant	Failed to Reject the Null Hypothesis
Gender		0.57	0.05	Significant	Reject the Null Hypothesis
Highest Educational Attainment	Interpersonal	0.99	0.01	Significant	Reject the Null Hypothesis
Years of Experience	Relations	0.13	0.18	Not Significant	Failed to Reject the Null Hypothesis
Relevant Seminars and Training		0.85	0.01	Significant	Reject the Null Hypothesis
Grade Level Assignment		0.07	0.48	Not Significant	Failed to Reject the Null Hypothesis

The table shows the significant relationship between the respondents' demographic and the teachers' interpersonal relations. It can be gleaned that gender (0.05), highest educational attainment (0.01), and the relevant training and seminars attended (0.01) established a significant relationship to teachers' interpersonal relations while age, years in teaching experience, and grade level assignment resulted in a no significant relationship. This means that when teachers acquire relevant training and seminars, they can capture techniques and strategies for nurturing good relations with their students and other stakeholders (Xie & Derakhshan, 2021).

Interpersonal relations refer to the ability of the teachers to communicate well and have a strong camaraderie with the learners (Li et al., 2020). This creates a positive learning environment where collaboration is observed among learners in completing academic tasks. It is important that in building a harmonious relationship between the teacher and the learners, factors are considered such as the diverse needs of the learners will be prioritized and addressed so that there will be more enriching learning experiences.

Table 25. Significant Relationship between the Classroom Management Skills Level and Work Performance Level of the Respondents

		R-value	p-value	Interpretation	Decision
Inside the Classroom	Teaching Skills	0.26	0.01	Significant	Reject the Null Hypothesis
	Management Skills	0.29	0.00	Significant	Reject the Null Hypothesis
	Discipline and Regularity	0.09	0.35	Not Significant	Failed to Reject the Null Hypothesis
Organization of the Lesson	Interpersonal Relations	0.23	0.02	Significant	Reject the Null Hypothesis
	Teaching Skills	0.14	0.15	Not Significant	Failed to Reject the Null Hypothesis
	Management Skills	0.41	0.08	Not Significant	Failed to Reject the Null Hypothesis
	Discipline and Regularity	0.93	0.01	Significant	Reject the Null Hypothesis
Interaction During the Lesson	Interpersonal Relations	0.91	0.01	Significant	Reject the Null Hypothesis
	Teaching Skills	0.49	0.00	Significant	Reject the Null Hypothesis
	Management Skills	0.57	0.00	Significant	Reject the Null Hypothesis
	Discipline and Regularity	0.41	0.00	Significant	Reject the Null Hypothesis
Teacher-Student Personal Communication	Interpersonal Relations	0.52	0.00	Significant	Reject the Null Hypothesis
	Teaching Skills	0.48	0.00	Significant	Reject the Null Hypothesis
	Management Skills	0.59	0.00	Significant	Reject the Null Hypothesis
	Discipline and Regularity	0.39	0.00	Significant	Reject the Null Hypothesis
Psychological and Social Classroom Environment	Interpersonal Relations	0.59	0.00	Significant	Reject the Null Hypothesis
	Teaching Skills	0.58	0.00	Significant	Reject the Null Hypothesis
	Management Skills	0.60	0.00	Significant	Reject the Null Hypothesis
	Discipline and Regularity	0.72	0.00	Significant	Reject the Null Hypothesis
	Interpersonal Relations	0.71	0.00	Significant	Reject the Null Hypothesis

The table reveals the significant relationship between classroom management skills and the level of work performance among the respondents. It can be gleaned from the table that these variables have a positive correlation with one another. Under the classroom management skills, teaching skills (0.01), Management Skills (0.00), and interpersonal relations (0.02) established a significant relationship while discipline and regularity (0.35) resulted in no significant relationship to the domain Inside the classroom. Organization of the lesson has having significant relationship to discipline and regularity (0.01) and interpersonal relations (0.01) while it does have a significant relationship to teaching skills (0.15) and management skills (0.08). Interaction during the lesson, teacher-student personal communication, and psychological and social classroom environment established a significant relationship to all domains under work performance (Hirsch et al., 2019).

It can be seen that most classroom management skills have a significant relationship to teachers' work performance (Wu et al., 2019). Inside the classroom, the way how the teacher facilitates and manages the classroom can greatly impact classroom management (Iqbal et al., 2021). Discipline regularity and interpersonal relations can also influence how the teacher will organize the lessons in such a way that it can establish a good ground for learning opportunities (Omar et al., 2020). Teaching skills, management skills, discipline and regularity, and interpersonal relations impact how the teachers interact with the learners, their way of communicating with the learners, and addressing the psychological and social needs of the learners in a diverse classroom (Warren, 2021).

Conclusions

Classroom management skills such as inside the classroom, organization of the lesson, classroom interaction, teacher-student personal communication, and psychological and social classroom are pivotal in shaping the work performance of the teacher. The theory of behaviorism is truly exemplified in this study wherein the teachers learned through the series of learning experiences by the association of the classroom management skills towards their overall work performance. Teaching skills, management skills, discipline and regularity, and interpersonal relations are key components of work performance which can be influenced mostly by the domains of classroom management skills. Strong and established classroom management skills are vital in creating a positive and conducive learning environment wherein the teachers can increase students' engagement. With this, the impact of classroom management skills on work performance goes beyond the teachers' professional reputation and extends to the truly rewarding field of education. This study strongly recommends the need to foster strong classroom management skills such as inside the classroom, organization of the lesson, classroom interaction, teacher-student personal communication, and psychological and social classroom among the teachers through relevant seminars and workshops. Teachers should be given every opportunity to grow and become the most effective and efficient teachers who mold young minds and create the leaders of today and tomorrow. It is also important that they will be given a program wherein closed monitoring of the application on how to manage a classroom is supervised. Teachers should do team teaching and should share best practices for improving and creating a positive learning environment. Future research can be initiated to explore further the different factors or variables affecting classroom management skills and work performance.

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